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Summary

This policy brief provides evidence analysis and recommendations drawing on research on justice within the twin transition and its governance in six EU Member States, undertaken during the first 15 months of the project

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Introduction and policy background

The EU has endorsed the objective of achieving climate-neutrality by 2050. Climate neutrality involves the reduction of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and the removal of any GHG emitted through carbon capture, utilisation and sequestration to achieve a net-zero emissions balance (European Council, 2024). To be effective, net zero must be permanent - i.e. removed GHG must not return to the atmosphere through measures such as deforestation or improper carbon storage (NetZeroClimate, ND).

As part of its climate-neutrality objective, the EU has recently focused on promoting the twin transition, understood as the ways in which digital technologies can enable the green transition. The EU aims to reduce emissions, enable a just transition while also maintaining economic growth.

There are several concerns regarding these priorities in relation to a just transition. First, there is mixed evidence about the degree to which the digital transition, and the trajectories of technological development more broadly, enable the green transition (Scholz et al. 2018; Söderholm, 2020; European Commission, 2022; Mercado et al, 2022). Second, there is growing evidence that reducing greenhouse gas emissions while prioritising economic growth will not enable net zero (Gough, 2017; Hirvilamni and Koch, 2020; Hirvilamni, 2020; Kallis et al, 2025). Third, the focus of the just transition remains on transitioning workers out of polluting industries (brown jobs) into environmental and renewable energy industries (green jobs). This is a narrow understanding of what a just transition would entail. It is restricted to providing supports to transition out of carbon-intensive male-dominated sectors, while completely omitting low-carbon, yet highly precarified and feminised sectors of the economy, as targets for support (Williams, 2018; Dukelow et al. 2024).

Arguably, to enable a just transition which 'leaves no-one behind' a more critical understanding of how the economy functions is required. One aspect of that will involve the redefinition and expansion of the term 'green jobs' to include all contributions which enable liveability within planetary boundaries.

Evidence and analysis

Transformative action towards a 'just transition' is conditioned by governance frameworks and economic models

The necessity to transition to an ecologically sustainable way of life globally is well established (IPCC, 2023). However, in practice green and digital transition policies are fragmented, one-dimensional, and not transformative. One reason for the lack of coordinated transformative effort at multiple levels (national, regional, global) is that those most responsible for GHG emissions do not perceive climate change as an existential threat by (Skillington, 2023: 160).

The social and sustainability policy literature emphasizes the importance of systems- thinking and transformative action. Yet, the likelihood of global communities' ability to achieve a just transition to a net-zero economy will be shaped by the dominant economic pathway taken. In addition, the ability of policy makers to design effective strategies that enable fair burden-sharing and insulate structurally disadvantaged groups against the negative impacts of transition policies may be hampered by key institutional structures.

Initial research indicates that countries with strong deliberative and collective bargaining institutions and processes are more likely to be able to implement the long-term strategies that a just transition requires. In contrast, liberal market economies that foster interest pluralism are less likely to be able to agree and implement long-term transition strategies (Petmesidou and Guillén, 2022: 326). Institutional structures could also influence the degree of public support for various eco-social supports (e.g. universal basic

services; participation income) and the specific forms best suited to those contexts (Koch, 2021; Laruffa et al, 2022; Krause et al, 2022). Gaining public support for the restructuring of social supports arguably requires medium-term, participatory, and deliberative citizen forums (Gough, 2016; Bonvin and Laruffa, 2022).

FITTER-EU analysed governance arrangements underpinning the twin transition in six EU Member States—Germany, Spain, Hungary, Ireland, Italy and Portugal. Drawing on country reports and stakeholder interviews, it mapped regulatory frameworks, institutional mandates and multilevel coordination mechanisms, assessing how national, regional and local actors interact with EU policy objectives.

Findings reveal highly heterogeneous governance models shaped by each country's historical, political and economic context. Common strengths include dedicated national strategies and growing stakeholder engagement ecosystems. However, 4 cross-cutting weaknesses persist: (i) fragmented decision-making across government tiers; (ii) misalignment between EU guidance and domestic priorities; (iii) limited horizontal coordination, resulting in separate digital and green policy streams; and (iv) inadequate inclusion of structurally vulnerable groups in agenda-setting and implementation.

In part, these weaknesses can be attributed to a lack of political will to facilitate transformative action. Facilitating labour-market transitions is a key element of the just transition, but greater clarity is needed on the interconnectedness of the welfare state and labour market policies. Under its current structure, the welfare state has limited capacity to support affected groups as part of the transition net zero (Galgóczy, 2023: 66). Furthermore, the literature indicates that the structure of welfare supports - wherein social policy measures are dependent on continued economic growth - is inefficient and in fact contributes to climate breakdown (Gough, 2017; Hirvilamni and Koch, 2020; Hirvilamni, 2020).

Three frameworks for an economic pathway are discussed in the environmental and social policy literature: green growth, doughnut economics and the foundational economy.

Within the **green growth** framework, the economy is defined by competition and trade in goods and services. The economy is separate from social supports (e.g. education, health) and environmental systems. Economic growth is prioritised through better transport links, attracting mobile investment to large projects, and training programmes to prepare people for the labour market. Success is measured through an increase in GDP, and this leads to the prioritisation of high-tech, knowledge-based industries and property-led regeneration (Wahlund and Hansen 2022). Social entitlements are funded through income and consumption taxes, which means that basic welfare services are reliant on a growing economy. Costs to the planetary ecosystems and within the care economy are significantly underestimated. Businesses which produce high emissions and damaging waste often do not pay for the full costs of their practices to planetary ecosystems (Regenerative Economics, ND; Heffron and McCauley, 2017).

Within **doughnut economics**, a focus on economic growth is criticized. Instead, the priority is placed upon improving wellbeing within planetary boundaries and the goal is for the economy to be regenerative and distributive by design. Doughnut economics divides the economy into four provisioning systems (Raworth, 2017: 78-86): i) the household, where care is provided through tasks such as cooking, cleaning, parenting, planning and organising activities; ii) the State, which supports the household through services (e.g. education, research and development, healthcare) and economic activities through infrastructure (e.g. roads, electricity grids, water treatment) as well as laws (e.g. labour laws, environmental protections); iii) the market, where goods and services are priced, bought and sold, providing goods and services to those who can pay; iv) the commons, a provisioning institution of free and open resources, such as natural, cultural, and digital resources. (Regenerative Economics, ND). Within this framework, all economic activity needs to take place within planetary boundaries and after providing for basic human needs. For these purposes, global corporate taxes and reforms of ownership of land, money, labour, technology, and

knowledge are required to increase revenues for public services and to balance incomes. In recognizing the societal contributions of activities in the household, by the State and through the Commons, doughnut economics places value on social and ecological needs and limitations (Regenerative Economics, ND, Raworth, 2017)

The **foundational economy** divides the economy into four parts (Froud et al., 2018: 3): i) the core economy, defined as noneconomic and comprising relations of care and connectedness; ii) the foundational economy, comprising the Material Foundational Economy (including utilities such as water, energy, agriculture and food, transport, housing) and the Providential Foundational Economy (including education, healthcare, elder care, social care); iii) the overlooked economy, comprising mundane, culturally specific purchases necessary for a good life (e.g. a haircut); iv) the tradeable competitive economy, referring to discretionary spending on other goods and services (e.g. high-end electronics, new cars). Within this framework, building socially embedded institutional structures that meet citizen needs within the material and providential economy is prioritised. It proposes social licensing as a key policy instrument (FEC, 2020: 8-9; Wahlund and Hansen, 2022) as well as taxes on wealth, progressive income taxes and a graduated land tax to fund and expand on services in the material and providential foundational economy. By differentiating domains of the economy, this framework prioritises the provision of services and goods consumed by all on a not-for-profit basis. Until recently, little attention was paid to what is termed the 'core economy', where unpaid care work, largely provided by women, is provided. Nonetheless, much work remains to be done on how a social licensing system could ensure environmental sustainability while meeting citizen needs, as sectors within the providential foundational economy such as education, health, and care are low carbon sectors, while sectors within the material foundational economy such as agriculture and food, energy, mobility and housing are some of the largest emitters of GHGs (Wahlund and Hansen, 2022: 182).

A key difference between these three frameworks is the value they place on domestic, social and ecosystem services. Within a green growth paradigm, the primary metric of success - GDP growth – excludes everything that cannot be quantified in monetary terms and values items that can be quantified in non-differentiated terms. In practice many domestic, social and ecosystem services are either omitted or counted as costs (Froud et al, 2018: 5). The purpose of doughnut economics is to fully account for the value of domestic, social and ecosystem services. Within the foundational economy, many social services are valued but, until recently, little attention has been paid to social services provided within the core economy (unpaid labour) and to ecological services.

At present, the focus of the EU is on enabling a twin transition while maintaining economic growth. This approach is appealing because it envisages a transition to carbon neutrality that is significantly enabled by technological development, without the need for a fundamental restructuring of economic models, land stewardship, energy use, and mindsets.

It is important to clarify the belief system underpinning technological development as this shapes actors' divergent views. Four stances can be identified with regard to the role of technology within the green transition:

1. **Techno-optimism** is the belief that there is no need for systems transformation because future technologies will 'fix' carbon emissions and environmental harm. Some techno-optimists envisage technological development remaining under human and social control while others believe in techno-determinism – i.e. that at least some processes of technological formation are beyond human control (Danaher, 2022: 10).
2. **Techno-pessimism** is the belief that processes of technological development and production do not lead to an improvement in the human condition.

3. **Techno-colonialism** refers to the ways in which digital development within current economic and political systems ‘reinvigorates and reshapes colonial relationships of dependency’ (Madianou, 2019: 2). Technological development incurs significant environmental and social costs to local communities and if these costs are not accounted for, and fair burden sharing is not enabled, a form of techno-colonialism is operative (Brevini, 2023: 28).
4. **Techno-realism** recognizes the political nature of technological development and proposes that it must remain under democratic social control. As investment and development decisions are based on what is of value to the people with the power to make such decisions, it proposes that we work to identify goals which will enhance the collective good and that we use technology to achieve those goals, thereby enabling sustainable, democratic and inclusive futures (Danaher, 2022; Sætra, 2023: 262; Bennahum et al 1998).

Yet the role of technology in enabling the transition to net zero remains unclear. Key issues include:

- **A disconnect between policies which aim to advance the green transition and those that aim to advance a digital transition.** While digital solutions can enhance sustainability, more evidence is required to establish the extent to which the digital transition will enable a substantive reduction in emissions (Andrae and Edler, 2015; Belkhir and Elmeligi, 2018; Malmodin and Lundén, 2018; Lange et al 2020; European Commission 2022).
- **Inadequate consideration of the societal impacts of digitalisation.** The digital divide, defined as a gap between those privileged and advantaged by new technologies and those who lack access, skills, resources or abilities to seize their full potential, is caused by factors such as the cost of digital tools, low effectiveness of accessibility tools and assistive devices, low level availability of training and upskilling programmes, and low levels of digital infrastructure (e.g. broadband access) in particular regions (Lussier-Desrochers et al., 2017; Lucendo-Monedero et al., 2019; Nijman and Wei, 2020; Tsatsou, 2021, 2022; Mubarak and Suomi, 2022; Van Kessel et al., 2022). Negatively affected groups can include low-income earners, older people, people with disabilities, rural populations, women, ethnic minorities and indigenous communities.

Transition policies tend to operate with a narrow understanding of a ‘just transition’ that is primarily focused on employment and a binary distinction between ‘green’ and ‘brown’ jobs

The need for the twin transition to be ‘just’ (‘leaving no one behind’) is widely recognised. However, the concept of justice in the twin transition has often been framed in terms of ‘jobs versus the environment’ which relates to threats posed to jobs by environmental regulations (Mandelli, 2022). As just transition policies focus on jobs losses in ‘polluting’ sectors, and job creation in the ‘green’ economy, there is a danger that some social groups will not be included in the just transition mechanisms. There are four issues to be emphasised in this context:

1. The ‘green’ element of twin transition policies tends to focus on a binary understanding of green vs. brown jobs, with green jobs defined as those that contribute to a green and sustainable economy and a just transition (ILO and UNEP 2008, pp. 35–36) and brown jobs, as ‘polluting’ and therefore to be phased out. Green jobs are often equated with employment in the environmental sector (ILO and OECD, 2022) often ignoring other sustainable activities, such as jobs in care and education. These activities, even if not directly contributing to either improving or damaging the environment, do contribute to the wellbeing of the people and the planet (Culot and Wiese, 2022). However, they are missing from the policies and targeted incentives promoting sustainability.
2. A focus on the creation of new jobs in the green economy risks shifting attention away from job losses, which is crucial in the pursuit of a ‘just transition’. The twin transition process offers significant opportunities for highly skilled professionals, yet it risks marginalizing workers from

carbon-intensive sectors, particularly those affected by industrial restructuring, who usually lack the required green or digital competencies. To ensure a just and inclusive twin transition, the implementation of targeted upskilling and reskilling programs, aligned with local labour market needs and backed by public-private partnerships, is essential. Such programs must be accessible, inclusive, and responsive to the specific socioeconomic contexts of affected regions and communities. This is particularly important considering that women tend to constitute a minority among workers in the industries which are key for the transition.

3. There are alternative understandings of the just twin transition as a fair and sustainable process of moving towards a post-carbon society (McCauley and Heffron, 2018:2) that go beyond the ‘jobs versus the environment’ mantra and take into consideration the broader context of societal transformation. The transition not only affects employment but also has an impact on the consumer side. For example, the shift to renewables requires households to change the way in which they consume energy, to retrofit their houses to be more energy efficient, as well as a shift to electric vehicles.
4. Policies to alleviate the impact of the transition on the consumer side usually provide a combination of both incentives (e.g. grants or tax credits) and penalties (higher energy bills or higher taxes for older vehicles) which, in most cases, disproportionately benefit higher-income households, while negatively impact structurally vulnerable groups. This might further exacerbate inequalities as, for example, those who cannot afford energy upgrades will experience rise in electricity bills. While energy poverty represents as a key concern in the transition process, the measures implemented by national governments tend to focus narrowly on short-term alleviation through subsidies, energy bill support, or social protection for structurally vulnerable groups, while longer-term supports such as energy upgrades often do not target the low-income population.

Lack of intersectional data on the impact of the twin transition on different structurally vulnerable groups means that these groups remain invisible for policymaking

On the European level, there is a plethora of open data that can be potentially used to analyse the impact of the transition on both the employment and the consumers’ side. However, data definitions do not always align to what is needed to accurately and fully assess twin transition impacts. Furthermore, data is often not disaggregated, thus not allowing for intersectional analyses. This leads to several difficulties with the data use. Several of issues have been identified when undertaking research in FITTER-EU:

- The definition of brown and green jobs varies, thus proving it difficult to assess which jobs should be taken into consideration (ILO and OECD, 2022). Green jobs are generally defined as those that contribute to the improvement of the environment and brown jobs as those considered as ‘polluting’. However, there is no single way of quantifying employment as either green or brown because different methods are applied, thus resulting in mixed results (DeVitta et al., 2024). Two ways of defining employment as green or brown are in place: top-down (sectoral) and bottom-up (occupational), but both approaches have limitations. The European Labour Force Survey provides data related to both sectoral and occupational measurements, which are extremely useful for an analysis of labour markets. However, the way the data is currently collected does not provide the level of detail needed to assess the green versus brown nature of the actual jobs. Furthermore, information on intersectional inequalities in employment within the green economy is also limited, as it does not enable a full understanding of the trends required for interventions to be more inclusive, ensuring that gender, racial, age and socio-economic background are accounted for in sustainable employment.
- Available data related to the consumer side does not allow for an in-depth analysis of the impact of the twin transition. For example, EU SILC provides data for energy poverty at household level

but does not cover data enabling an analysis of the relationship between moving to renewable energy and change in energy costs, or the type of household availing of the energy upgrades. Furthermore, very little can be assessed in relation to inequalities, as energy poverty data allows for an analysis of gender and age profile of the household, but not for other dimensions such as ethnicity.

Policy implications and recommendations

Beyond ‘green jobs’ – rethinking policies for a just transition

Evidence emerging from the analysis shows that the twin transition should be considered a long-term and complex process giving rise to policy implications in the area of employment and consumers protection:

- Green jobs should be expanded to include other sustainable activities positively impacting on people’s wellbeing such as health, care or education.
- With regards to employment policies, the focus should be on re-skilling/up-skilling programmes and more generally in life-long training, to ensure that skills match the new needs of the impacted sectors. Re-skilling and up-skilling activities should be tailored to value existing workers’ skills as well as the cumulated know-how of workers at risk of losing their job. Properly designed re-skilling and up-skilling can limit mismatch between job losses and new jobs created.
- A just transition must go beyond labour market considerations and focus also on impacts on consumers, specifically in relation to poverty (e.g., energy poverty, transport poverty). Evidence points that targeted measures to improve efficiency in specific sectors can also positively impact specific types of poverty, such as reducing energy bills or transport costs while reducing GHG emissions, if they are easily accessible by people in low-income brackets.

Acknowledging ‘green growth’ constraints for achieving environmental and social justice goals

The transition to a net-zero economy will require supports for affected groups to be put in place. For this, both social and technological innovation is required. The configurations of social supports need to be transformed as part of the transition to net zero.

The green growth paradigm does not envisage significant restructuring of the economy, labour market and social supports. Both doughnut economics and the foundational economy frameworks stress that the current structure of the economy, labour market and social supports generate inequalities and environmental harms. Although they differ in their accounting for social and ecological services, both propose that a well-designed redistributive economic model that prioritises wellbeing rather than growth would improve living standards for all.

The challenges facing policy makers are significant. There are good practices such as integrated climate-digital roadmaps and regional innovation clusters, but coordination gaps remain, hampering efficiency and diluting accountability. Treating the transitions holistically, rather than as parallel tracks, is critical for policy coherence and for maximising social and economic spill-overs. Enabling transformative action, including restructuring the economy and social supports would need significant public support, the beginnings of which could be achieved through citizen assemblies for example.

Further reflection on the usefulness of GDP as a measure of economic success is also timely. Recent trends indicate that GDP growth has not led to poverty reduction in many countries, with wealth and income inequality increasing over the past 50 years (Earle et al, 2018; UNDP, 2023; Kerr and Vaughan, 2024). A long-time criticism of GDP is that it excludes everything that cannot be quantified in monetary terms and

values items that can be quantified in non-differentiated terms. This leads to contestable values and omissions (Raworth, 2017: 39-40; Froud et al, 2018: 5).

Although governments increasingly acknowledge the need to shift to a plurality of indices that account for the social and environmental impacts of economic activity, this does not address two more fundamental problems with a reliance on GDP metrics:

- The privileging of the GDP number encourages an understanding of the economy as productionist - where activity generates earned income from providing goods and services with use value. This view has questionable relevance in the context of present-day financialised capitalism. It excludes rentier wealth and household balance sheets - providing a very limited understanding of patterns of inequality (Raworth, 2017; Froud et al, 2018: 6).
- The problem not only relates to what is included and accorded value, what is measured as a cost and therefore not 'productive', and what is excluded. The problem is that the economy is made up of heterogeneous and incommensurable objects that cannot be simply added up together. For example, affordable healthcare makes a very different kind of contribution to the overall 'economy', than an inexpensive fast-fashion dress, the production of which generates significant social and environmental harms (Froud et al, 2018: 5-6)
- A focus on GDP targets orients policy makers to prioritise the development of high-growth sectors such as technology. It does not lead to the prioritisation of local liveability in terms of access to good quality basic services; the creation of decent work and quality jobs; and ensuring businesses deliver social benefits to local communities (Wahlund and Hansen, 2022: 178). In effect then technological innovation is prioritised over social innovation. However, to enable a just transition, technological innovation arguably should work in service of social innovation. Taking the stance of a techno-realist, we can acknowledge the importance of technological development and work to identify and develop the kinds of technology that enhances wellbeing within planetary boundaries.

Recommendation 1: Awareness Raising

The scale of transformation required to address climate breakdown suggests that policy makers need to formulate programs for foundational provision on a sustainable, multi-scalar basis, considering the social and ecological dimensions of the local-to-global interlinkages of foundational goods and services (Raworth, 2017; Froud et al, 2018; Wahlund and Hansen, 2022: 183).

At local and regional level, multiple projects across the EU are already engaged with local stakeholders, they have identified key requirements of a just transition underpinned by human rights and they have developed achievable goals, often adapting elements of alternative economic paradigms to suit local conditions. Four initial actions can be taken to develop an evidence base and facilitate stakeholder engagement on enabling a just transition at local and regional level:

- Desk research and the production of briefing notes to develop local policy makers' understanding of the current structure of economic priorities, the labour market and social supports in their region and the strengths and weaknesses of alternative economic pathways
- Engage with and learn from local authorities which are experimenting with alternative economic models such as those developed by doughnut economics or the foundational economy collective.
- Develop a medium to long term local engagement strategy with communities as an ongoing element of the just transition.
- Engage with local communities to develop plans for a just transition across relevant sectors. Prioritise the achievement of environmental and social objectives but facilitate imaginative, evidence-based and well-informed thinking on how that can be best achieved.

Recommendation 2: Multi-criteria analysis of costs and benefits

In economies which support foundational liveability, all households regardless of income or wealth would have access to good quality, affordable, accessible and reliable basic goods and services provided within planetary boundaries. Relevant policy makers could explore the possibility of developing metrics which:

- Measure the environmental and social harms of energy and ICT extraction, production and waste disposal. Although individual policymakers will not be able to conduct a full analysis of the social and carbon footprint of component parts of technologies, significant awareness raising on the social and environmental costs of resource extraction is needed. Arguably the onus should be on technology companies to enable informed policy making and consumer choices. Brevini (2023: 30-31) suggests several governance mechanisms, such as: accountability for those who own clouds and data centres; stronger public awareness about the environmental and social justice implications of adopting a piece of smart technology; transparent calculations of the energy used to produce, transport, assemble, and deliver technology; requirements that manufacturers lengthen the lifespan of smart devices and provide spare parts to replace faulty components; or educational programs to enhance green tech literacy and raise awareness of the costs of hyper consumerism, as well as the importance of responsible energy consumption.
- Measure access to foundational provision (e.g. housing, utility supply, healthcare) within planetary boundaries. As a first step, one method to calculate current patterns would be to work down subtractively from gross income, calculating spending on objects located in the material foundational, providential foundational, overlooked and competitive parts of the economy respectively (Froud et al, 2018: 8).

Building a dynamic, adaptable and inclusive model of twin transition governance

From the report conclusions we identified five general policy recommendations. These recommendations point to an overall dynamic, adaptable governance model with a strong inter-ministerial and inter-governmental coordination able to: i) embed EU objectives more systematically in national action plans; ii) establish institutional inclusive stakeholder forums to give voice to marginalised communities; iii) enhance transparency to rebuild public trust.

Recommendation 1: Establish integrated, multi-level governance structures

Create a legally anchored ‘twin-transition’ framework with permanent inter-ministerial and inter-governmental coordination bodies—at national, regional and local levels. This framework will allow to align green with digital objectives, both with budget allocations and timelines. This will ensure coherent planning, implementation and evaluation across all tiers of governance and in all phases including financing.

Recommendation 2: Strengthen local capacity and streamline funding mechanisms

Tackling technical capacity gaps in small municipalities is of primary importance in all European Union regions but it is even more important in under-resourced regions. To achieve this aim, it is recommended that every EU- or nationally-funded investment to be implemented at local level is paired with technical-assistance packages (training for SMEs and public servants, model tenders, expert pools). It is also recommended that a simplified audit/reporting rules for local authorities is negotiated with financing authorities (the Commission or central national authorities) while implementing quicker antifraud measures (with the support of technological solutions). The expected outcome is an acceleration of project uptake and absorption of cohesion and RRP funds.

Recommendation 3: Mainstream social equity and justice across all policies

Integrate social-justice checks into every policy cycle by implementing ex-ante intersectional impact assessments on gender, poverty, disability and rural/urban divides, while addressing intersectional equity targets in affected sectors (e.g. energy-poverty reduction, rural broadband quotas, transport poverty solutions, retraining guarantees). Promote social dialogue and civil society participation especially in coal, carbon intensive or digitally lagging regions, to establish and fund ‘just-transition pacts’ to prevent the rise of new inequalities.

Recommendation 4: Institutionalise Broad Stakeholder and Civil-Society Engagement

Current consultation is often ad hoc, and there is a need for systematic participation. Institutionalise civil society, social partner and citizen panel co-decision at each policy stage (design → implementation → monitoring) and provide public transparent information on how feedback changed final measures to further promote active participation.

Recommendation 5: Enhance transparency, monitoring and adaptive learning

Launch a single, open-data dashboard to track financial flows, technical and social-equity indicators (CO₂ reductions, connectivity gains, poverty alleviation), alongside regular ‘twin-transition stress-tests’ led by an independent science-policy interface. Integrate mission-oriented innovation programmes with ex-novation (phased-outs phases of obsolete practices) to enable evidence-based course-corrections.

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